

FIELD EVALUATION OF SELF-PROPELLED REAPER BINDER AND MANUAL HARVESTING OF PADDY

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Abstract

The field evaluation of self-propelled Reaper binder was carried out for harvesting of paddy crop at Gadchiroli. The average effective field capacity and field efficiency of the self-propelled reaper binder was found to be 0.35 ha/h and 92 % respectively whereas the effective field capacity in manual harvesting was 0.076 ha/h. Fuel consumption of self-propelled reaper binder was 0.71 lit/hr, 1.94 lit/ha. Average value of harvest losses in mechanical harvesting was 0.94 percent only where as average value of harvesting losses in manual harvesting was 1.84 % which is more than that of mechanical harvesting. The cost of operation for self propelled reaper binder and for manual harvesting were 1755.76 Rs/ha and 3343 Rs/ha respectively in comparison to manual harvesting along with time saving and early field preparation for Rabi crops. The per cent saving in the cost of operation and time are 48.21 % and 79.22 % respectively by harvesting of paddy with self propelled reaper binder over manual harvesting.

Keywords-Paddy Harvesting, Reaper & Binder, Mechanical harvesting, Field performance

Introduction

In the Eastern Vidarbha Zone of Maharashtra, India paddy mono-cropping system is followed in 7.165 lakh hectares. Out of total man hours required for paddy cultivation around 20 % of it is required for harvesting and bundle making. Timely harvest of crop is vital to achieve better quality and higher yield of the crop. The shortage of labour during harvesting season and vagaries of the weather causes greater losses to the farmer. Harvesting by locally available tools causes delay in the harvest and has direct effect on the yield. It is therefore essential to adopt the mechanical method so that the timeliness in harvesting operation could be ensured as well as the cost of operation can be reduced and field losses will be minimized to

Table 1: Specification of the self-propelled reaper binder

Sr. No.	Particulars	Specifications
1	Make	BCS
2	Model	Standard
3	Manufactured by	BCS India Pvt. Ltd.
4	Cutting width	4 feet
5	Height of cut	5-7 cm
6	Engine	10.2 hp Diesel,
7	Gear	4 Forward & 1 Reverse

The cut crop is gathered at the centre of machine continuously in standing position by the collecting fingers provided in front of the machine. A spring actuated lever is provided to control the size of the bundle of the reaped crop. As soon as the pressure of the reaped crop increases above the spring tension, the releasing of the bundle and tying knot around the bundle is done simultaneously by the machine. The tied bundle is then released gently on the ground at the centre of the machine. The seat is provided for operator and below the operators seat the steering wheel is provided which is operated by the foots. The steering is also done by breaking one of drive wheels.

The testing of self-propelled reaper binder has been carried out on farmers field at Gadchiroli district. The parameters that were measured by using standard formulae's during field test are as follows:

- Speed of travel
- Fuel consumption
- Total operating time
- Field efficiency
- Effective field capacity
- Harvesting losses

Result & Discussion

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increase the productivity and production on the farm. Considering the above facts and constraints feasibility testing of self-propelled reaper binder for harvesting and bundle making of paddy have been carried out in Sonapur – Gadchiroli, Maharashtra. Specific.

Objective

- 1) To test the field performance of the self-propelled reaper binder.
- 2) To study the economics of use of self-propelled reaper binder.

Material And Methods

The self-propelled reaper binder machine is used for cutting the paddy crop and making the bundles of the crop by the machine automatically. It consists of reciprocating cutter bar for cutting the crop.

The results of field performance based on test conducted are summarized in Table 2.

The average plant height, row spacing, and height of cut were 85-90 cm, 10 -15 cm, 4.5 cm respectively. The mean values of forward speed, fuel consumption, effective field capacity, and harvesting losses were 2.7 Km/h, 5 lit/ha, 0.20 ha/h, and 8.03 % respectively. While harvesting of paddy it was observed that paddy fields are small and not of even size which causes more turning losses resulting into less forward speed, more fuel consumption and less effective field capacity.

Conclusion

The average effective field capacity and field efficiency of the mechanical harvester i.e. self propelled reaper binder was found to be 0.35 ha/h and 92 % respectively where as the effective field capacity in manual harvesting was 0.076 ha/h. Fuel consumption of self propelled reaper binder was 0.71 lit/hr, 1.94 lit/ha. Average value of harvest losses in mechanical harvesting was 0.94 percent only where as average value of harvesting losses in manual harvesting was 1.84 % which is more than that of mechanical harvesting. The cost of operation for self propelled reaper binder and for manual harvesting were 1755.76 Rs/ha and 3343 Rs/ha respectively in comparison to

manual harvesting along with time saving and early field preparation for Rabi crops. The per cent saving in the cost of operation and time

are 48.21 % and 79.22 % respectively by harvesting of paddy with self propelled reaper binder over manual harvesting.

Table 2: Test results of self propelled reaper binder and manual harvesting of paddy crop

Sr. no	Parameter	Self propelled reaper binder				Manual harvesting
		Trial				
		1	2	3	Avg	
1	Crop	Paddy	Paddy	Paddy	-	Paddy
2	Variety	PKV-HMT	PKV-HMT	PKV-HMT	-	PKV - HMT
6	Height of plant , cm	85-90	85-90	85-90	85-90	85-90
7	Row spacing , cm	10-15	10-15	10-15	10-15	10-15
8	Number of tillers per sq. m	350-450	350-450	350-450	350-450	350-450
9	Height of cut, cm	6	6	6	6	10
10	Condition of crop	erect	erect	erect	-	erect
11	Diameter of stem at Cut, cm /mm	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
12	Grain moisture content, %	16.15	17.65	15.43	16.41	16.41
13	Straw moisture content, %	30 - 35	30 - 35	30 - 35	30 - 35	30 - 35
14	Actual area covered (ha)	0.2	0.2	0.2	-	0.2
15	No. of Labours	1	1	1	1	16
16	Total time of operation (min)	62	58	60	60	165
17	Effective working width (cm)	120	120	120	120	-
18	Forward speed (kmph)	2.8	2.6	2.7	2.7	-
19	Theoretical field capacity (ha/hr)	0.4	0.40	0.4	0.4	-
20	Effective Field capacity (ha/hr)	0.21	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.076
21	Field efficiency %	46	48	45	46.34	-
22	Labour requirement, man-hr/ha	5	5	5	5	213.67
23	Fuel consumption (lit/ha)	5.1	4.8	5.1	5	-
24	Fuel consumption (lit/hr)	1.02	0.96	1.02	1.0	-
25	Yield from 1m ² (gm)	410	419	427	418.67	415
26	Harvesting losses (g/m ²)	8.2	7.6	8.3	8.03	9.1
27	Shattering losses, %	0	0	0	0	0
28	Uncut loss,%	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
29	Harvest losses (Shattering+Uncut) % (a+b+c)	8.2	7.6	8.3	8.03	9.1
30	Cost of operation (Rs/ha)	1660.66	1702.38	1814.26	1755.76	3343
31	Cost of operation (Rs/hr.)	674.22	612.85	566.04	620	250

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